

Assessing Leadership styles Practices in Public University Libraries: Insights from North-East Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: A leader with an appropriate leadership style motivates, inspires, and energizes personnel to perform effectively and efficiently towards achieving organizational goals. So, this study focused on transformational, transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles to identify the types of leadership styles practiced in the 14 public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria.

Method: The study adopted a survey research design with the population of 618 library personnel across the 14 public universities libraries in North-East, Nigeria. A sample size of 237 was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970). A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients ranged from 0.72 to 0.98. Descriptive analysis of means and standard deviation was used to analyze the data.

Findings/results: The study showed that transformational leadership was the most practiced leadership style followed by transactional leadership style. Laissez-faire was reported to be the least practiced leadership style.

Implications: The study concluded that transformational leadership is the most practiced style, among the three leadership styles (transformational, transactional and

laissez-faire) practiced in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria. followed by transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles.

Conclusion/recommendations: As showed by the study, the public university libraries in the North-East, Nigeria practiced transformational and transactional leadership styles. While avoiding practicing laissez-faire leadership style. Some recommendations were made based on the findings.

Keywords: Laissez-faire, leadership style, North-East, Nigeria, public university libraries transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style.

1. Introduction

Leadership styles are different ways and manners used to influence the activities of subordinates through appropriate communication towards achieving organizational goals. The aim of leadership style is to enable leaders to motivate their subordinates to enthusiastically do what needs to be done in an appropriate manner. According to Getachewu, (2023). the main determinate of success or failure of organization group or a country is the effectiveness of its leaders. Similarly, Nwokocha and Iheriohanma, (2015) postulated that leadership facilitates the accomplishment of the organizational goals and objectives. Moreso, Urhefe-Okotie and Eruvwe (2025). Argued that the library leadership and the leadership styles practiced by the librarians are said to determine, to some extent, how the library achieves its organizational goals and objectives.

According to Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2014), the different styles of leadership may influence organizational performance or effectiveness. Also, Nwaigwe (2015) argued that there is no generally accepted leadership style somewhat an appropriate leadership style is based on circumstances and situations on the ground. The effect of any leadership style on the work force, particularly on the subordinate librarians, will come to bear if the leadership of the library achieves its goals. Edet et .al (2024). highlights the importance of adopting an appropriate leadership style to overwhelmed the obstacles of poor leadership. Likewise, Owera (2019) complements that appropriate leadership style comprises listening, encouraging and supporting staff, nurturing skilled decision-making and team-building.

To understand different styles of leadership and come up with a more detailed viewpoint of the construct, this study, focused on transformational, transactional, and Laissez-Faire leadership styles, as identified by Arikan (2020) as the three major leadership styles, to explore the types of leadership styles practiced in the 14 public university libraries in the North-East, Nigeria. It is important to note that leaders mostly adopt different leadership styles, and the most effective leadership style normally

depends on the situation, characteristics, followers, and the missions at hand (Yukl, 2006) cited in Umoh (2023). Yet, there is a knowledge gap in the types of leadership styles practiced in public university libraries in the Northeastern region of Nigeria; it is this gap that this study aims to fill.

2. Statement of the Problem

Leadership in academic libraries is not only about managing staff; it includes inspiring a shared purpose, empowering staff, and responding to dynamic academic changes in such a way that promotes libraries' values to the mother institutions and university communities. A choice of poor leadership styles in academic libraries may lead to indiscipline, which affects productivity and decreases the rate of service delivery to zero. (Akparobore & Omosekejimi, 2020). Similarly, Limsila and Ogunlana (2008) claimed that the application and adoption of the right leadership style improve work performance and ensure staff productivity. Despite increasing demands on university libraries to meet educational needs of the mother institutions and the roles of appropriate leadership styles in university libraries, literature and observation showed that there are still limited understandings of the kind of leadership styles practiced in the public universities, particularly in the under-researched region of North-East Nigeria.

This gap is exacerbated by regional issues and challenges such as security instability, limited resources, and changing administrative structures, which affect leadership practices specifically compared to other parts of the country. Subsequently, there is a persistent need to identify and contextualize the leadership styles practiced within the public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria, to address the current ineptitudes and contribute to evidence-based development of leadership. Without such assessments, library services may continue to face stagnation, staff disengagement, and underperformance in meeting academic goals of the library and the university at large.

3. Research Question

What are the types of leadership styles practiced in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria?

4. Literature Review

4.1 Overview of leadership styles in academic libraries

University libraries are the backbone of every university and are expected to have a higher degree of efficacy and effectiveness in the provision of information resources and services for teaching, learning, and research, as well as meeting the needs of their diverse users. To achieve these effectiveness and efficacy, the university library must prepare for appropriate leadership styles that are central in coordinating and

performing the organizational tasks to ensure organizational success. Robust leadership is required for activities like inspiring nurses and other employees to work efficiently and making them feel appreciated and respected in their workplace. (Thakur, Verma, & Sharma, 2019). According to Arumuru (2019), the leadership styles practiced in the libraries influence the work attitude of the library staff, as the commitment and satisfaction of the library personnel are hinged on the leadership of the library. without successful leadership employees find it hard to keep their competitiveness (Lussier & Achua, 2007). With such a leader would be able to practice two more different styles depending on the situation.

Previous studies investigated the leadership styles practiced in academic libraries. Example: Tarsik, Kassim, and Nasharudin (2014) examined leadership styles practiced by Malaysian university librarians and found that the majority of the libraries adopted and practiced transformational leadership style, followed by laissez-faire and transactional leadership style. Similarly, Thanh and Quang (2022) explored different types of leadership styles: transformational, transactional, laissez-faire leadership styles, and employee engagement from Vietnam's public sector and discovered that the level of an employee's engagement to work depends largely on leadership styles practiced. Al-Owaidi, Saleh, and Benmechirah (2023) examined the relationship between leadership styles and job satisfaction of teachers and administrative staff of Babylon University, Iraq, and found a strong and positive relationship between democratic leadership style and job satisfaction, but an opposite relationship between autocratic leadership style and job satisfaction. Also, the findings showed no correlation between laissez-faire leadership and job satisfaction.

Similarly, Hongo, Kwanya, Mwai, and Kiplang'at (2024) explored the influence of leadership styles on the performance of University Libraries in Kenya and revealed that most university librarians practiced democratic and transformational styles. The study concluded that laissez-faire and bureaucratic leadership have negative effects on library performance. Moreso, Enakrire, et al. (2025). Examined the roles of leadership styles and information professionals to support academic institutions and published that information professionals need the application of different styles of leadership, such as transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire, to strengthen the academic activities in their institutions.

Udom and Okonkwo (2022) investigated the influence of transactional and transformational leadership styles on library staff productivity in federal university libraries of South-South Nigeria. They found a strong relationship between transformational and transactional leadership styles and staff productivity in the Federal University libraries of South-South Nigeria. Thus, transactional leadership style was seen to be strongly related to staff productivity. Udom and Okonkwo (2022) investigated the influence of transactional and transformational leadership styles on

staff productivity in federal university libraries of South-South Nigeria. The finding revealed a strong relationship between transformational and transactional leadership styles and staff productivity.

4.2 Transformational Leadership style

One of the fundamental components of transformational leadership style is getting personnel involved in organizational decision making through empowering, encouraging motivating to ensure higher productivity. Transformational leaders' performance in ways that stimulate and inspire those concerning them through bestowing meaning and challenge to the followers' work (Long, Yusof, Kowang, & Heng, 2014). The transformational leadership is needed today; it can inspire staff to do their best, improve their skills, and enable them to advance their intellectual levels. A transformational leader is capable of urging their subordinate to achieve beyond expectations. (Alqatawenah, 2018).

Anderson (2017) described transformational leadership as a set of behaviors or activities undertaken by the leader to improve overall organizational performance and outcomes. Bernard (1977), as cited by Anderson (2017), identified idealized influence, individualized consideration, inspirational motivation, and intellectual stimulation as the daily transformational behaviors of transformational leadership.

4.3 Transactional Leadership style

Unlike transformational leadership, the fundamental goals of transactional leadership are to uphold order, enforce regulations, and guarantee that protocols are followed. This leadership approach uses a system of incentives, sanctions, and rewards for good behavior. (Ugwu et al., 2020). Makambe and Moeng (2020) maintained that transactional leadership prioritizes short-term goals and immediate results over long-term developments. It involves negotiating values and rewards to meet followers' material and psychic needs, often prioritizing adherence to established procedures over creativity and long-term vision (Jun & Lee, 2011). Erkutlu, (2008) stated that transactional leadership involves continuous monitoring of staff performance to take corrective actions when performance deviates from expectations.

Skogstad et al. (2007) positioned Transactional leadership focuses on teamwork by promoting collaboration and effective organizational cultures. Transactional leaders also work to enhance subordinates' skills through ensuring training and development. In this regard, the personnel are essential organizational resources, and only by improving their quality and capabilities can they achieve sustainable development.

4.4 Laissez-faire Leadership style

Lewin et al. (1939) cited Skogstad, in Einarsen et al. (2007), described laissez-faire as a leadership style where the leader has been chosen and physically occupies the position, but abdicates from the duties and responsibilities he or she was assigned to. Consequently, a laissez-faire leadership does not only mean a lack of presence, but zero leadership, which implies not meeting the expectations. By giving workers, the freedom to express themselves and take responsibility for their work, this strategy can create an atmosphere that supports personal development, especially in trying circumstances.

Laissez-faire approach can be effective in some contexts, particularly with highly skilled and motivated employees; it can also lead to significant challenges (Quadri et al., 2021). Laissez-faire leadership may not align with the goals of an organization that requires high levels of productivity across all levels. In such cases, the lack of direction and guidance can result in inefficiencies and lower productivity (Anbazhagan & Kotur, 2014; Thanh & Quang, 2022). The hesitancy of laissez-faire leaders to make decisions and their tendency to avoid active engagement can create an environment where team members are unclear about their roles and responsibilities, leading to confusion and a lack of direction (Robert & Vandenberghe, 2021)

5. Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey research design. This design was chosen to ensure efficiency and determine the types of leadership styles in public university libraries in the North-East, Nigeria. The population for this study comprises of 618 library personnel from the 14 public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria: Army university library, Bi'u (32 staff), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa university library, Bauchi (82 staff), Federal university library, Gashua (26 staff), Federal university library, Kashere, (43 staff), federal university of health science library, Azare (12 staff), Ramat library university of Maiduguri (109 staff), federal university library, Wukari (42 staff), Modibo Adama university library, Yola (43 staff), Adamawa state university library (47 staff), Borno state university library (26 staff), Gombe state university library (52 staff), Taraba state university library (60 staff), Bauchi state university library (26 staff), and Yobe state university library (19 staff), These libraries served the entire public universities from the geographical representation across states Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe.

The researcher utilized a simple random sampling technique to ensure unbiased sampling. Sampling is defined as the process of selecting a sample from the entire population, enabling generalizations about the population to be made based on the

sample. (Mweshi & Sakyi, 2020). The sample size for the study was 237, determined by the Krejcie and Morgan (1970)

The data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Leadership Styles Practices in Public University libraries in Northeast, Nigeria was used for data collection. The instrument contained Likert-scale items to measure the types of leadership styles practiced (Taye, 2020). The questionnaire items were subjected to content validity through expert review, and the reliability was confirmed via Cronbach's alpha of a pilot study (n = 15) (Cronbach, 1951). For ethical consideration, an official letter was sent to each of the institutions for approval. The researcher dispersed questionnaires in person to ensure clear instructions. The data collection was completed over 6 weeks across the 14 universities. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and standard deviations) were used for data analysis and presentation to determine the types of leadership styles practiced. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 27.

Table 1.0: *Questionnaire Administered and Response Rate:*

Response	Participants	Percentage (%)
Distributed	237	100.0
Returned	180	76
Not returned	57	24

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Out of 237 questionnaires distributed, 180, representing 76% were retrieved and found usable and adequate for analysis, as Mugenda and Mugenda (2008) testified that the statistically significant response rate for statistical analysis should be at least 50%. A response rate of 50% is adequate for analysis and reporting; a rate of 60% is good, and a response rate of 70% and above is excellent. Table 1.0 shows the copies of the questionnaire administered and the return rate.

Research question 1: What are the types of leadership styles practices in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria?

Respondents were simply asked to describe the leaderships of their libraries in terms of leadership style of transactional, transformational and Laissez-faire on a five (5) point scale of High extent (5) to Not at all (1). The result is shown in Table 1. The overall mean scores show that respondents described the leadership of their libraries as positively high (> 2.90).

Table 2.0: Leadership styles practiced in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria.

SN	Leadership styles	Mean	Std.
1	Transformational	3.21	0.12
2	Transactional	3.15	0.12
3	Laissez-Faire	2.35	0.29
	Grand Mean	2.90	0.48

Table 2.0 the table above showed that majority of the respondents (3.21) and (3.15) reported that their leaders are observed practicing transformational leadership styles and transactional leadership styles while (2.35) reported Laissez-faire leadership styles in their libraries.

The analysis of the types of leadership style practiced in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria. Namely Transformational (3.21) This implies that library leaders often inspire, motivate, and encourage staff to explore new ideas and innovative approaches. Respondents confirmed that their leaders help them develop their potential, provide personal support, and introduce them to new knowledge and skills.

Transactional leadership style (3.15) also within the high-level category. This style is characterized by clear task assignments, monitoring of performance, and the use of rewards or disciplinary measures to maintain order. The responses suggest that transactional behaviours, such as setting clear expectations and evaluating performance based on set goals, are fairly common in the libraries. This shows that library leaders also emphasize structure, adherence to procedures, and accountability.

Laissez-faire leadership recorded the lowest prevalence, with a mean score of (\bar{x} = 2.35), indicating a low level of agreement. This suggests that most library leaders adopt hands-off approach to leadership, they do not interfere with subordinates' decision, and believes that employees can do their work independently with little supervision or no guidance from the leader. Also, respondents generally disagreed with statements suggesting their leaders neglect involvement in security matters or fail

to monitor compliance. Overall, the study found a high level of leadership engagement in the libraries, with a dominant inclination toward transformational and transactional approaches and minimal adoption of laissez-faire practices.

6. Discussion of Findings

The research question aimed to identify the types of leadership styles practiced in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria. Findings reveal a predominant use of transformational and transactional leadership styles among public university library leaders, with minimal adoption of laissez-faire practices.

This finding aligns with the study of Quadri et al. (2023), who investigated the leadership styles practiced in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria, and found that transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership styles were all practiced in university libraries accordingly. Similarly, Hongo et al. (2024) examined the influence of leadership style on Kenyan university libraries and revealed that democratic and transformational leadership styles were most commonly practiced. This indicates a regional variation where democratic leadership, characterized by participative decision-making, plays a more significant role alongside transformational practices. Oguntuase, Okhakhu, and Fasae (2025) explored the impact of different leadership styles on collection development practices in academic libraries in Ekiti State, Nigeria and found that academic libraries practiced different leadership styles, with the democratic leadership style as the most practiced, followed by autocratic leadership and laissez-faire leadership styles.

The outcome aligns with the study by Koohang et al. (2020), which investigated the impact of leadership on employees' intention to comply with organizational information security policies. Their study found that effective leadership plays a critical role in shaping compliance behaviour by fostering an environment conducive to adherence to security protocols. Shal et al. (2024). explored the relationship between the leadership styles adopted by academic librarians and their openness to artificial intelligence (AI) and concluded that implementation AI in academic libraries is more likely to happen under transformational leadership styles, with transactional leadership being associated with suboptimal outcomes a noteworthy association is observed between the perception of ease of use and the adoption of laissez-faire leadership.

Similarly, Mayowa-Adebara and Opeke (2019) conducted a study on the influence of leadership style on employee commitment in South-West Nigeria university libraries, and identified transformational leadership as a key predictor of employee commitment in university libraries. While their findings support the present study's emphasis on transformational leadership, they did not highlight transactional leadership, suggesting possible regional differences in leadership dynamics and their impact on staff behavior. Kalu and Okpokwasili (2021) investigated leadership styles and Job

Performance in academic libraries in Port Harcourt, Rivers state, and reported that the democratic leadership style was the most practiced and effective, resulting in high employees' productivity. Similarly, Akidi and Chukwueke (2020) explored university Librarians leadership styles and staff productivity in some selected university libraries in Imo State, the findings of the study revealed the adoption and practice of transformational, democratic and autocratic leadership styles in selected university libraries in Imo State. Out of the leadership styles examined, transformational leadership style was exceedingly practiced and followed by democratic leadership style.

Ugwu and Okore (2020) also found that both transformational and transactional leadership styles significantly influenced knowledge management practices among librarians in Nigerian university libraries. However, transformational leadership had a more substantial impact, reinforcing its effectiveness in cultivating a knowledge-sharing and compliant organizational culture. In another related study, Fasola (2024) investigated the role of leadership styles in digital transformation efforts within private university libraries in South-West, Nigeria. The study emphasized that transformational leadership positively influenced the adoption of digital technologies, which are foundational to robust information security frameworks.

Furthermore, Unobe and Sahabi (2023) explored the relationship between leadership styles and job performance among librarians in public university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. They discovered that both transactional and transformational leadership styles are commonly practiced, with transformational leadership being more dominant. These findings further suggest that leadership style plays a pivotal role in influencing performance outcomes, including compliance behavior. On the other hand, Oguntuase et al. (2025) investigated the relationship between leadership styles and collection development practices in academic libraries in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study found that democratic leadership styles positively influenced collection development, implying that inclusive leadership approaches may also extend to better information security compliance.

Contrasting perspectives are also evident in other studies. For instance, Lazarus, et al. (2019) leadership and management practices in the 21st century academic libraries and found that leaderships of the 21st century in academic libraries should act different from those of those of the 19th and 20th century in order to efficiently lead and succeed in the extremely competitive global economy and similarly, Chukwusa, (2018) who investigated the influence of autocratic leadership style as obstacle to success in academic libraries and found that autocratic leadership style avoids the use of original ideas to solving a problem so, library leaders should learn to exercise curb in the use of the autocratic leadership style in the running of their libraries. Similarly, Wong (2017). Who conducted a review of leadership and leadership development in

academic libraries found that librarians view leadership as an act of influence, and comprehend that leadership does not necessarily come through formal leaders.

7. Conclusion

This study investigated the types of leadership styles practiced in public university libraries in North-East, Nigeria. The findings revealed that transformational leadership stands out as the most impactful leadership style in the public university libraries in North-east, Nigeria, while transactional leadership also contributes positively and laissez-faire leadership has no or little impact.

8. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations was made.

Library management should encourage leaders to adopt transformational and transactional leadership approaches that inspire staff, promote vision-sharing, and foster proactive behaviours. Also, laissez-faire leadership should be discouraged as it has no significant impact.

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